

WATER-SOLUBLE CHITOSAN-GOLD COMPOSITE NANOPARTICLES: PREPARATION BY RADIOLYSIS METHOD

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1 Introduction

Preparation of metal nanoparticles is one of the major research areas in nanotechnology. Metal colloid science had begun with the experiments of Michael Faraday on gold sols in the mid-nineteenth century [1]. Many methods for preparation of metal nanoparticles have been developed over the years since Faraday's experiments. Gold nanoparticle has received much attention to study since it has been reported many advantages [2]. The potential application of gold metallic nanoparticles and their nanocomposites has been widely studied in many fields: (i) physics, e.g. analytical probes; (ii) biology, e.g. biological markers; (iii) chemistry, e.g. catalysts; (iv) electronics and (v) materials [3]. It is well known that metallic nanoparticles has tendency to aggregate in the solution due to their small size [1]. Therefore one of the effective ways to avoid the agglomeration of the particles is to use the stabilizing agents or protective agents, such as thiols, surfactants, and polymers [4]. The stabilizer can control the particle size as well as prevent the agglomeration of metal particles.

Most of the synthetic methods, such as chemical reduction, which frequently used for preparing metal colloidal solution, involve the reducing and stabilizing agents. These toxic chemicals unavoidably result in environment [5]. The purification of the by-products is essentially important for using the nanoparticles in the biological application. In order to avoid the toxic by-products as well as to eliminate pollution to the environment, biopolymer has been considered to use as a stabilizer in metallic nanoparticle production. Chitosan is a biopolysaccharides consisting of β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-2-acetamido-2-deoxy- β -D-glucose (chitin) and β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-2-amino-2-deoxy- β -D-glucose (chitosan) linked with glycosidic linkage. It has

been reported to use as a biopolymer based stabilizer for metallic colloidal particles [6]. Corma et al. [7] reported that gold was supported on the chitosan which has the ability to act as reducing/stabilizing agent in the formation of gold nanoparticles. Based on the literature report, the organic solutes in the form of water-soluble, such as polymers, is well known as an excellent stabilizer in forming colloidal nanoparticles [8].

Gold nanoparticles have been successfully synthesized by numerous methods, such as chemical reduction [9], photochemical reaction [10], sonochemical technique [11], radiolysis [12] and so on. For the later, radiolysis method, it offers fast, simple, effective and environmental friendly over other synthetic processes. Only a few reports according to the synthesis of gold nanoparticle using electromagnetic radiation such as microwave [13], UV light [14], and gamma radiation [12] has been studied. To our knowledge, the strategy to synthesize gold nanoparticle under mild condition of aqueous water soluble chitosan using gamma irradiation has not yet been reported. Therefore, we present herein, the synthesis and characterization of gold nanoparticles in water-soluble chitosan (Au-WSCS) via radiolytic synthesis using gamma irradiation. The effects of the gamma-irradiation dose and the concentration of gold precursor and water-soluble chitosan on the particle formation were investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Chemicals

Chloroauric acid (HAuCl₄) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. Chitosan (% DD = 95 and M_v = 7 × 10⁵ Da) was supplied from Seafresh Chitosan (Lab) Company Limited, Thailand. Acetic acid

(CH₃COOH) was purchased from Lab Scan Analytical Science. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was bought from Carlo Erbar reagent, USA. All chemicals were used without further purification.

2.2 Preparation of Gold-Water Soluble Chitosan Composite Nanoparticles (Au-WSCS-CNPs)

A stock solution of water-soluble chitosan (WSCS) (0.1% w/v) was prepared. WSCS (50 mL) was added to the different concentrations of 0.1 and 0.5 mM HAuCl₄ (150 mL). The mixtures were γ -ray irradiated with the doses of 0.01-50 kGy using the ¹³⁷Cs Gamma MARK I and the ⁶⁰Co Gammacell 220 irradiators with the dose rate of 0.428 kGy·h⁻¹ and 7.7 kGy/h, respectively.

2.3 Characterization of Au-WSCS-CNPs

UV-vis spectra of colloidal Au-WSCS-CNPs solutions were recorded over a wavelength of 400-700 nm by a Libra S32 Spectrophotometer (Biochrom, UK). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were taken by a Hitachi H7650 zero (Hitachi High-Technology Corporation, Japan). Colloidal solution was prepared by placing a drop of Au-WSCS-CNPs sample on a copper grid and dried in the desiccators at room temperature for 24 h. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra were recorded by a Tensor 27 Bruker spectrophotometer with 32 scan, 2 cm⁻¹, resolution. X-ray diffraction (XRD) morphology was carried by using a Bruker AXS X-ray diffractometer with CuK α as an X-ray source at 50 kV and 100 mA.

3 Results and Discussion

The radiolytic methodology using γ -ray irradiation offers many advantages for the preparation of metallic nanoparticles as mentioned above. The e_{aq}⁻ produced from water radiolysis reduce metal ions to zero-valent metal particles. In this way, additional reductants are not necessary [15]. Generally, radiolysis of aqueous solutions involves the radiolytic reduction. In the present work, gold nanoparticles were synthesized in aqueous water-soluble chitosan. Therefore, the mechanism involved in our system should be radiation induced chain scission of chitosan and radiation induced reduction of gold ions to gold particles. In aqueous solution, γ -rays induce water radiolysis to form solvated electrons (e_{aq}⁻), hydroxyl radicals (OH[•]), hydrogen

atoms (H[•]), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), hydrogen gas (H₂) (Eq. (1)). The OH[•] and H[•] species react with polysaccharide molecules by H-abstraction on carbon atoms (C₁-C₆) within glucosamine unit (Eq. (2)) [16]. Radicals can form at C₁ and C₄ atoms that involve the scission of 1-4 glycosidic linkages (Eq. (3)) [6]. The e_{aq}⁻ species reduce gold ion (Au³⁺) to gold atom (Au⁰) (Eq. (4)) and many neutral Au⁰ can form clusters as seen in Eq. (5).

3.1 Physical Appearance and Particle Formation of Au-WSCS-CNPs

The γ -ray irradiated WSCS solutions containing HAuCl₄ exhibited more intense purple color than those of non-irradiated samples (Fig. 1(a)). The Au-WSCS-CNPs solutions turned from yellow to purple indicating the formation of gold nanoparticles after γ -ray irradiation. The samples irradiated with the γ -ray doses of 1-50 kGy (Fig. 1 (e-g)) exhibited more intense purple than those irradiated with the γ -ray doses of 0.01-0.2 kGy (Fig. 1 (b-d)). It was evidently found that the color intensity of HAuCl₄ containing WSCS increased when the γ -ray doses increased.

Fig. 1. Appearance of Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in the HAuCl₄ concentrations of (A) 0.1 and (B) 0.5 mM, containing 0.1% (w/v) of WSCS solution, after γ -ray irradiation with various doses: (a) 0, (b) 0.01, (c) 0.04, (d) 0.2, (e) 1, (f) 10 and (g) 50 kGy.

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Formation of Au-WSCS-CNPs was confirmed by UV-vis spectrophotometry. The absorption bands of the Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized with various γ -irradiation doses were clearly observed. The broad surface plasmon resonance (SPR) absorption band of Au-WSCS-CNPs solutions appeared at 540–570 nm (Fig. 2). It can be seen that the intensity of the absorbance increased with increasing the irradiation doses. This result from UV-vis spectra corresponded to the increasing of color intensity as described previously. For the highest γ -ray dose of 50 kGy, the absorbance decreased with a red shift of SPR band. This indicated that the particle size and/or the formation of Au nanoparticles tend to aggregate [17]. It can be suggested that the γ -ray doses affected the absorbance or the number of Au particles formed in the solution.

Fig. 2. UV-vis absorption spectra of Au-WSCS-CNPs formed in the different HAuCl₄ concentrations of (A) 0.1 and (B) 0.5 mM, containing 0.1% (w/v) WSCS solution, after γ -ray irradiation with various γ -ray doses.

UV-vis spectra (Fig. 2) also implied the effect of HAuCl₄ concentration on the particle formation. Increasing the concentration from 0.1 mM (Fig. 3(a)) to 0.5 mM (Fig. 3(b)) significantly increased the absorbance of the resulted Au-WSCS-CNPs. Fig. 3 also reveals that with increasing the γ -ray dose from 1-50 kGy of both WSCS concentrations, the absorbance did not further increase. Therefore, it is considered that the γ -ray dose of 1 kGy is the optimal radiation dose for the preparing Au-WSCS-CNPs under the given concentrations.

Fig. 3. Absorbance at λ_{max} of Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in the different HAuCl₄ concentrations of (■) 0.1 and (■) 0.5 mM, containing WSCS solution, after γ -ray irradiation with various doses.

3.2 Structural Characterization of Au-WSCS-CNPs

To verify the possible interaction between WSCS and Au nanoparticles, the FT-IR spectra for WSCS and Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in 0.1 mM and 0.5 mM HAuCl₄ in the present of 0.1% (w/v) WSCS after γ -ray irradiation with the dose of 0.2 kGy were measured and shown in Fig. 4. The FT-IR spectrum of WSCS shows the major peaks at 899, 1089, 1423, 1630 and 3350 cm⁻¹ belonging to pyranose ring, glucoside, amine, acetamide and hydroxyl groups, respectively [14]. Compared with Fig. 4(b) and (c), as shown in Fig. 4(a), there was an increase in the intensity of the C=O absorption peak at 1630 cm⁻¹ implying the increase of carbonyl group. Fan et al. [13] explained that the production of the carbonyl groups might be from the oxidation of hydroxyl groups in the WSCS by HAuCl₄. Compared with the spectrum of WSCS, an appearance of N-H bending vibration at 1523 cm⁻¹ of Au-WSCS-CNPs (Fig. 4(b)

and (C)) referred to an interaction between Au nanoparticles and nitrogen atoms of the WSCS molecules, by wrapping around Au nanoparticles to facilitate them stable in the solution [13]. In addition, an increasing peak at 1016 cm^{-1} where assigned to C-O bonding for Au-WSCS-NPs was also observed as a result of a formation of a

Fig. 4. FT-IR absorption spectra of (a) WSCS (b) Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in 0.1 mM HAuCl₄ and (c) Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in 0.5 mM HAuCl₄, containing 0.1% (w/v) WSCS solution, after irradiation with the dose of 0.2 kGy.

Fig. 5. XRD pattern of (a) WSCS (b) Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in 0.1 mM HAuCl₄ and (c) Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in 0.5 mM HAuCl₄, containing 0.1% (w/v) WSCS solution, after γ -ray irradiation with the dose of 0.2 kGy.

coordinate bond between Au nanoparticles and nitrogen/oxygen atoms in WSCS molecules [14]. The formation of colloidal Au-WSCS-CNPs solution was also confirmed by XRD pattern. Fig. 5 shows diffraction peaks for pure WSCS (Fig. 5(a)) and Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in the 0.1 mM (Fig. 5(b)) and 0.5 mM (Fig. 5(c)) HAuCl₄ containing 0.1% (w/v) WSCS aqueous solutions. The spectrum included four strong Bragg diffraction peaks at 38.2° , 44.4° , 64.7° and 77.6° that can be assigned to the (111), (200), (220) and (311) planes [18]. As seen in Fig. 5 with the diffraction peaks, the peaks can be interpreted as a face-centered cubic (fcc) of Au and a crystal structure in nature [14, 19].

3.3 Shape and Size of Au-WSCS-CNPs

Shape and size of Au-WSCS nanoparticles synthesized using γ -ray were observed by TEM. Fig. 6 shows the example of TEM images of Au-WSCS-CNPs formation in the different HAuCl₄ concentrations after γ -ray irradiation with various doses. Most particles of Au-WSCS-CNPs were spherical shape with an average diameter of 7-30 nm. Considering the particle formation of Au-WSCS, it can be concluded that WSCS exhibited to prevent the aggregation of the Au-WSCS nanoparticles. TEM images imply the successful formation of Au-WSCS-CNPs via radiolysis method. To describe the effect of the irradiation dose as well as the relationship between the absorption intensity to the particle size of Au-WSCS-CNPs, the comparative graph plots were formulated as seen in Fig.7. It was found that the particle sizes of Au-WSCS-CNPs are affected by radiation doses. The particle size reduced when the irradiation dose increased from 0 to 10 kGy. On the contrary, the γ -ray dose as high as 50 kGy, the particle size slightly increased.

For the HAuCl₄ concentration of 0.1 mM, the average diameter particle sizes reduced from 22 nm to 7 nm for γ -ray dose of 0-10 kGy and the particle size increased up to 14 nm after irradiated with the γ -ray dose as high as 50 kGy (Fig. 7(A)). In the case of 0.5 mM HAuCl₄, it was found that the particle diameters reduced from 27 nm to 8 nm for γ -ray dose of 0-10 kGy and increased to 12 nm for γ -ray dose of 50 kGy (Fig. 7(B)). It was suspected that the particle possibly agglomerated when the γ -ray irradiation dose increased up to 50 kGy. In addition,

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Fig. 6. TEM images of Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in the different HAuCl_4 concentrations of (A) 0.1 and (B) 0.5 mM, containing 0.1% (w/v) WSCS solution, after γ -ray irradiation with the dose of (a) 0, (b) 0.2 (c) 1 and (d) 50 kGy.

it has been reported that the size of metal nanoparticles can be altered by the concentration of precursor [15]. In this study, the different HAuCl_4 concentrations of 0.1 and 0.5 mM in the WSCS solution were also studied. The particle sizes of Au-

WSCS-CNPs synthesized using 0.1 mM and 0.5 mM HAuCl_4 exhibited insignificant different within the range of 22-7 nm and 27-8 nm, respectively.

Compared with the SPR band intensity, the particle sizes determined from TEM images related to the SPR band intensity as indicated by a contrary tendency in reducing the particle size with increasing the absorption intensity. The small particle size, the higher absorbance intensity implied the higher number of the particle and surface area.

Fig. 7. Comparative plot between the particle size and the SPR band intensity at λ_{max} of Au-WSCS-CNPs synthesized in the HAuCl_4 concentrations of (A) 0.1 and (B) 0.5 mM, containing 0.1% (w/v) WSCS solution, after γ -ray irradiation with various doses.

4 Conclusions

A novel gold-water-soluble chitosan composite nanoparticles (Au-WSCS-CNPs) was successfully prepared via radiolytic methodology using γ -ray irradiation. The particle size of Au-WSCS-CNPs can be controlled by γ -ray dose. The average particle size of Au-WSCS-CNPs was as small as 7 nm with spherical shape. The radiolytic methodology would

serve as a mild, simple and effective procedure to synthesize Au nanoparticles.

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